

**THE CONCEPT OF LEXICAL OCCASIONALISM AND
THEIR PLACE IN THE SYSTEM OF OCCASIONALISM****O.Yu.Tokhtasinova****Kokan DU associate professor, c.f.s.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19448161>****ARTICLE INFO**

Received: 01st April 2026

Accepted: 04th April 2026

Online: 06th April 2026

KEYWORDS*occasionalism, occasional word,
occasional meaning, neologism,
ordinary, ozus, potential word***ABSTRACT***This article presents lexicographic interpretations of occasionalisms, the relationship of neologisms and occasionalisms, and the analysis of the differences between them based on four criteria.*

The study of the interrelation of language and speech phenomena is one of the urgent issues of linguistics. The word, which is an important element of language, is a linguistic unit outside of speech, and a speech unit in speech. This fact, on the one hand, indicates the mutual differentiation of language and speech, and on the other hand, their close connection. The fact that language and speech units are sharply different phenomena has been expressed in studies.

Unlike linguistic units, speech units arise as a product of the speech process. Because the speech process is a situation, a communicative field, for the use of linguistic units, the manifestation of their inherent semantic aspects. Therefore, the speech process creates certain conditions for the realization of the meanings of various words. Along with all linguistic units, words and phrases characteristic of the individual style of a particular creator are also used in speech. They can remain as a speech phenomenon in the form of words specific to the text or the individual style of a certain creator, or they can quickly become active in speech activity, become part of the structure of the language, and become its normative unit. Such words are called neologisms and occasionalisms in linguistics. In linguistics, different opinions have been expressed about neologisms and occasionalisms. Some people consider neologisms and occasionalisms to be the same concept, while others emphasize that they are different. First of all, let's turn to dictionaries. O.S. Akhmanova defines neologism as follows:

“1. A word or phrase created to express a new subject or a new concept.

2. A new word or phrase that does not have the right to “civility” in the general language and is therefore considered to be characteristic of a separate, often passive style of speech. Style neologism. A word that is perceived as a novelty when found in a particular genre of a literary work. A word used in everyday life, but not in works of art. Stylistic neologism. A neologism created only by the author of a work of art and usually not widely used. Compare: hapax eiremenon, potential word”.

“Hapax eiremenon (hapax legomenon, occasional word). A word or phrase used “once” by a speaker or writer for a certain situation”.

“A potential word is 1) a simple or compound word that does not exist in reality (i.e., even if it existed, it has not yet been used in speech), but can be created at any moment in accordance with the productive word-forming pattern of a language; 2) words that are an element of a phraseological unit and have the property of being separated from it as an independent unit.”

The purpose of giving these definitions in detail in the dictionary is to provide a clear expression of the concepts of occasionalism and neologism. As we understand it, O.S. Akhmanova considers occasionalism to be a neologism. Now let's pay attention to other dictionaries.

The term occasional word or occasionalism (derived from the Latin word occasionalis - accidental (случайный)) is used to refer to a unit of speech that is created in a certain piece of speech, lives in this text, does not pass into another text, and is not accepted as a stable norm of the language.

D.E. Rosenthal and M.A. Telenkova explain neologism as follows: “Neologism (Greek neos - new + logos - word, concept). A word or phrase of speech (speech turnover) created to express a new object or a new concept... When a word enters the sphere of widespread use, it ceases to be a neologism... Some neologisms of the Soviet era have become obsolete...”

Stylistic (individual - stylistic) neologism. A neologism created by the author of a literary work with a specific stylistic purpose, but which does not have the potential for widespread distribution and is not included in the vocabulary of the language.” The same dictionary also discusses the concepts of occasionalism and occasional: “Occasionalism. A word created on the basis of an unproductive word formation pattern, used only in certain contexts. Compare: stylistic neologism”.

“Occasional (Latin occasionalis - accidental). Not corresponding to generally accepted usage, having an individual characteristic, not dependent on a specific context (compare: usual)”.

Let's also look at the definition given to the term usual.

“Usual. A word, phraseological expression, grammatical construction, etc., that meets the requirements of use of a certain language community (compare: occasional)”.

“Usual (Latin usus - custom, rule, use). A word, stable combinations, forms, constructions, etc., accepted for use by representatives of a certain language.”

Comparing the definitions given, it becomes clear that the lexicographers tried to avoid considering occasionalism as a neologism. The descriptions given to the stylistic neologisms they indicated are essentially close to the descriptions of occasionalism, but in the first there is also the idea that “it is not part of the vocabulary of the language”, which is not included in the description of the second word. The impression is created that occasionalisms are units that differ from neologisms, but the authors cannot categorically say that they are not neologisms.

In A. Khojiev's “Explanatory Dictionary of Linguistic Terms”, the following definition is given: “Occasionalism is a word created on the basis of an unproductive template, used only in the same text, an individual style neologism. For example, like ice cream (морозный)”. In

addition, the dictionary also provides an understanding of the occasional meaning: "Occasional meaning (lat. occasionalis - accidental). A meaning that has not yet been formed in the semantic structure of the word, but is realized in a certain individual use: The flowers of science and art are whole, gathered for conversation (Oybek). Compare: usual meaning".

This explanation provides clear information about the Uzbek occasional word and occasional meaning. It seems that "occasionalism" can be used synonymously with the term "individual style neologism", since dictionaries provide concepts that are regulated and subject to certain norms. Since occasionalisms are given attention in dictionaries, we think that this should be taken into account when listing their characteristics.

A study of the existing scientific literature has shown that the nature of the appearance of occasionalisms seems to be related in a certain sense to the concept expressed by the neologism. However, these linguistic phenomena are different from each other. Below we express our opinion on this issue.

The relationship and difference between a new word (neologism) and an occasionalism can be analyzed based on the following four criteria:

1. The presence or absence of an author (creator). This criterion is not important for defining a new word. A new word is a fact of language. Occasional words are a fact of speech. One of the important features of occasional words is their belonging to an author. Most of these words are not reproduced in memory. They are created by a person for the first time. Of course, it is impossible to know who the occasional words found in oral speech belong to, this is hampered by the instability and variability of oral speech, but written speech makes it much easier to find the creator of occasional words. In a word, occasional words are fundamentally related to a specific person - the creator of this occasional word. In a language, each of its facts, including new words, is significant only socially, that is, as an absolutely ownerless unit belonging to the community of all people who are the owners of this language. Like all words in a language, when their owner was later forgotten, new words were generalized and their belonging to specific authors was forgotten.

2. The measure of novelty of a word is important, but it is not absolute and mandatory for all new words. This measure is mandatory only for modern new words, relevant (active) new words, where the novelty of the word is felt. For example, merchant, collective farm, ministry, and the like began to be used in the 90s, and today their novelty has disappeared.

The genetic core and fundamental basis of the concept of neologism is the quality of novelty of the word. "So, neologism is an extremely relative concept. It is a typical law that neologisms lose their novelty and move to the ranks of ordinary, normal words. When a word appears, while retaining its novelty, it retains the characteristics of a neologism. A new word remains a neologism until it is completely assimilated by the language; until it is added to the active reserve of the lexicon, that is, until it loses its unnaturalness." However, this feature is not inherent in all new words. (Relatively) new words of the past do not have this quality, but it is present in current new words. It should not be forgotten that relatively new words were current new words at one time. Because current new words inevitably turn into relative new words over time. A sense of novelty in current new words is an obligatory feature that this new word must have. In general, the characteristic of novelty for a new word is absolutely undoubted. This characteristic is the basis of the general concept of neologism. In this sense,

the following thoughts of E. Begmatov on the essence of neologism are true: "A neologism is a new or newest word according to the time of its appearance, in which a shade of novelty is clearly felt. A neologism is a word that has just appeared in the language. It is a lexeme that has not yet passed into the ranks of normative words of the language. Therefore, neologisms are words belonging to the passive layer of the lexical composition." The whole difficulty lies in the fact that when analyzing this characteristic, it cannot be characterized numerically or formally. This makes it very difficult for linguists to objectify and describe the studied characteristic. For example, it is very difficult, if not impossible, to say how long a word that has appeared in the language will retain its novelty (and at the same time its neologism status). The more semantically relevant a word that appears in a language, that is, the stronger the speech need for it, the more rapidly it is integrated into the language process, the faster its novelty fades and the shorter its term as a neologism. For example, a number of today's new words such as minister, region, district, governor, telebridge, tamaddinoma, nakfakhor, presentation have lost their novelty due to their extreme relevance and frequent use.

Thus, new words are directly included in the general chain of historical changes in the language and, therefore, are themselves subject to these changes. This situation, which is one of the fundamental conditions and signs of the concept of neologism, is alien to occasional words that are linguistically introduced due to the criterion of historical time, as a separate fact of speech.

3. Finally, it should be said that new and occasional words are very different in terms of the criteria for entering or not entering the language vocabulary. The fact that new words enter the language vocabulary (or rather, are part of the language) does not cause any doubt. The history of the literary language testifies to this. Occasional words are a pure product of speech. A word that has arisen can be called a new word only if it is a fact of language and is separated from the status of occasionality (or does not have such a status at all). E. Begmatov expresses the following thoughts about new words and their linguistic features in the Uzbek language: "Along with the nature of obsolescence, renewal is also inherent in the vocabulary of the language. As has been considered in the language, just as it is natural for some words to become obsolete and go out of use, so too is it

As E. Begmatov rightly noted: "The novelty or obsolescence of a word depends on the period of its appearance in the language. The applicability or obsolescence of a word depends on the functional activity or passivity of lexemes". In this sense, each word can be called a neologism in principle in relation to the time of its appearance. In this case, it is only necessary to determine when this or that word appeared in the language. For example, words such as collective farm, state farm, tractor, tractor driver, pioneer are considered neologisms of the 30s of the 20th century in the history of the Uzbek literary language. Over time, they lost their novelty, became widely used in the minds of the language owners, and became part of the active word class. However, today the words collective farm, state farm, pioneer have gone out of use and become historical words.

In the 30s of the 20th century, a group of new words emerged based on various types of word formation. They are relatively variable, and their functions are studied in connection with a specific historical period, a specific text. That is why it is necessary to talk separately

about the neologisms of the 40s, 50s, 60s, 70s, 80s, and 90s of the 20th century. The neologism of each period lives, having undergone various historical evolutions, gradually losing its quality of novelty. "The creation of new words in a language is a product of the historical development of the language, its movement forward in time. Therefore, all newly formed words in a language can be studied not only synchronously, but also diachronically, that is, from the point of view of their emergence at a certain period of language development." It follows from this that the concept of a new word is diachronic.

Occasional words have not only the property of being unmemorable, but also the property of being one-time and synchronic-diachronic in application. Thus, they are irrelevant to historical time. Therefore, such words cannot be called neologisms.

Thus, the criterion of time is necessary in defining a new word, but as indicated above, it is not absolute, but is considered relative.

Based on the above evidence, the following definition of a new word can be given: A new word is a word that is undergoing the initial stage of its historical life in the language, has a touch of novelty.

Thus, the term new word cannot be applied to occasional words due to their specific properties. A new word is a completely diachronic concept that links one or another fact (in this case, the fact of the expression of a new word) to a certain fact. Occasional words are fundamentally "unhistorical" because they are deprived of their "internal" history, because they are used once, most of them are not recalled in memory, and because they are synchronously-diachronically mixed, they are deprived of a long life in the language. The emergence of occasional words is in any case connected with historical facts that are external to them. For example, an occasional word may have a specific historical date of its emergence, be associated with its specific historical identity, its author, as well as with the reasons and circumstances that led to its emergence. Such words, unlike stable (usual) words, are alien to real history. They are deprived of periodically changing characteristics, that is, they are deprived of internal development in the field of lexical meaning, stylistic coloring, expressiveness, word-forming structure, etc.

The historical life of an occasional word is of a punctuated nature, since its use, in principle, does not extend diachronically.

Occasional words do not affect the temporal aspect of the language, that is, they cannot be called either new words or stable words, regardless of the time of their appearance. A new word can be imprinted in written texts, but when it is born in oral speech, it ceases to exist with the end of the speech process. Occasional words belonging to writers of different periods of the history of the Uzbek literary language (M. Shaikhzoda, H. Olimjon, U. Nosir, Chulpon, Mirtemir and others) have survived to our days in the text in which they were created and have not undergone any changes, including neither becoming obsolete nor becoming active; this could not have happened because they were far from the factor of historical time. Therefore, in this case, occasional words are far from the factor of historical development and change.

These characteristics of occasional words, namely their fundamental "immortality," have given rise to the widespread notions of them as "permanently new words" or "eternal new

words.” In short, it is neither correct nor expedient to include occasional words in the list of new words. They are individual units of speech with their own unique characteristics..

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